
CONTINUOUS DEUTSCH UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE AND CONTINUOUS KRAUS CONJECTURE

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Abstract: Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces and $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$, $\{\omega_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ be 1-bounded continuous Parseval frames for a Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Then we show that

$$(1) \quad \log(\mu(\Omega)\nu(\Delta)) \geq S_\tau(h) + S_\omega(h) \geq -2 \log \left(\frac{1 + \sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \omega_\beta \rangle|}{2} \right), \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau \cap \mathcal{H}_\omega,$$

where

$$\mathcal{H}_\tau := \{h_1 \in \mathcal{H} : \langle h_1, \tau_\alpha \rangle \neq 0, \alpha \in \Omega\}, \quad \mathcal{H}_\omega := \{h_2 \in \mathcal{H} : \langle h_2, \omega_\beta \rangle \neq 0, \beta \in \Delta\},$$

$$S_\tau(h) := - \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_\alpha \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_\alpha \right\rangle \right|^2 d\mu(\alpha), \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau,$$

$$S_\omega(h) := - \int_{\Delta} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_\beta \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_\beta \right\rangle \right|^2 d\nu(\beta), \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_\omega.$$

We call Inequality (1) as **Continuous Deutsch Uncertainty Principle**. Inequality (1) improves the uncertainty principle obtained by Deutsch [*Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 1983]. We formulate Kraus conjecture for 1-bounded continuous Parseval frames. We also derive continuous Deutsch uncertainty principles for Banach spaces.

Keywords: Uncertainty Principle, Hilbert space, Frame, Banach space, Deutsch uncertainty, Kraus Conjecture.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Let $\mathcal{H}$ be a finite dimensional Hilbert space. Given an orthonormal basis $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for $\mathcal{H}$, the **(finite) Shannon entropy** at a point $h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau$ is defined as

$$S_\tau(h) := - \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_j \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_j \right\rangle \right|^2 \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{H}_\tau := \{h \in \mathcal{H} : \langle h, \tau_j \rangle \neq 0, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$. In 1983, Deutsch derived following uncertainty principle for Shannon entropy [3].

Theorem 1.1. (Deutsch Uncertainty Principle) [3] *Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be two orthonormal bases for a finite dimensional Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Then*

$$(2) \quad 2 \log n \geq S_\tau(h) + S_\omega(h) \geq -2 \log \left(\frac{1 + \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|}{2} \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau \cap \mathcal{H}_\omega.$$

In 1988, followed by a conjecture of Kraus [9] made in 1987, Maassen and Uffink improved Inequality (2) [12].

Theorem 1.2. (Kraus Conjecture/Maassen-Uffink Uncertainty Principle) [9, 12] *Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be two orthonormal bases for a finite dimensional Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Then*

$$2 \log n \geq S_\tau(h) + S_\omega(h) \geq -2 \log \left(\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle| \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau \cap \mathcal{H}_\omega.$$

In 2013, Ricaud and Torresani [13] showed that Theorem 1.2 holds for Parseval frames.

Theorem 1.3. (Maassen-Uffink-Ricaud-Torresani Uncertainty Principle) [13] *Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be two Parseval frames for a finite dimensional Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Then*

$$2 \log n \geq S_\tau(h) + S_\omega(h) \geq -2 \log \left(\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle| \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau \cap \mathcal{H}_\omega.$$

Recently, Banach space versions of Deutsch uncertainty principle have been derived in [11]. To formulate them, we need some notions. Given a Parseval p-frame $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for $\mathcal{X}$, we define the **(finite) p-Shannon entropy** at a point $x \in \mathcal{X}_f$ as

$$S_f(x) := - \sum_{j=1}^n \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left| f_j \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{X}_f := \{x \in \mathcal{X} : f_j(x) \neq 0, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$. On the other way, given a Parseval p-frame $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ for $\mathcal{X}^*$, we define the **(finite) p-Shannon entropy** at a point $f \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^*$ as

$$S_\tau(f) := - \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left| \frac{f(\tau_j)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{X}_\tau^* := \{f \in \mathcal{X}^* : f(\tau_j) \neq 0, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$.

Theorem 1.4. [11] (Functional Deutsch Uncertainty Principle) *Let $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{g_k\}_{k=1}^m$ be Parseval p-frames for a finite dimensional Banach space $\mathcal{X}$. Then*

$$\frac{1}{(nm)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \leq \sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right)$$

and

$$\log(nm) \geq S_f(x) + S_g(x) \geq -p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g, \|y\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(y)g_k(y)| \right) \right) > 0, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g.$$

Theorem 1.5. (Functional Deutsch Uncertainty Principle) Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^m$ be two Parseval p -frames for the dual $\mathcal{X}^*$ of a finite dimensional Banach space $\mathcal{X}$. Then

$$\frac{1}{(nm)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \leq \sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right)$$

and

$$\log(nm) \geq S_\tau(f) + S_\omega(f) \geq -p \log \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^* \cap \mathcal{X}_\omega^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g(\tau_j)g(\omega_k)| \right) \right) > 0, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^* \cap \mathcal{X}_\omega^*.$$

In this paper, we derive continuous versions of Theorem 1.1, Theorem 1.4 and Theorem 1.5. We also formulate a conjecture based on Theorem 1.2. We wish to say that functional continuous uncertainty principles are derived in [10].

2. CONTINUOUS DEUTSCH UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE AND CONTINUOUS KRAUS CONJECTURE

In the paper, $\mathbb{K}$ denotes $\mathbb{C}$ or $\mathbb{R}$ and $\mathcal{H}$ (resp. $\mathcal{X}$) denotes a Hilbert space (resp. Banach space) (need not be finite dimensional) over $\mathbb{K}$. We use (Ω, μ) to denote a measure space. Continuous frames are introduced independently by Ali, Antoine and Gazeau [1] and Kaiser [8]. In the paper, $\mathbb{K}$ denotes $\mathbb{C}$ or $\mathbb{R}$ and $\mathcal{H}$ denotes a finite dimensional Hilbert space.

Definition 2.1. [1, 8] Let (Ω, μ) be a measure space. A collection $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ in a Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$ is said to be a **continuous Parseval frame** for $\mathcal{H}$ if the following conditions hold.

- (i) For each $h \in \mathcal{H}$, the map $\Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto \langle h, \tau_\alpha \rangle \in \mathbb{K}$ is measurable.
- (ii)

$$\|h\|^2 = \int_{\Omega} |\langle h, \tau_\alpha \rangle|^2 d\mu(\alpha), \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}.$$

We consider the following subclass of continuous Parseval frames.

Definition 2.2. A continuous Parseval frame $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ for $\mathcal{H}$ is said to be **1-bounded** if

$$\|\tau_\alpha\| \leq 1, \quad \forall \alpha \in \Omega.$$

Note that if $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is a Parseval frame for a Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$, then $\|\tau_j\| \leq 1, \forall 1 \leq j \leq n$ (see Remark 3.12 in [7]). We are unable to derive this for continuous frames. Given a continuous 1-bounded Parseval frame $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ for $\mathcal{H}$, we define the **continuous Shannon entropy** at a point $h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau$ as

$$S_\tau(h) := - \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_\alpha \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_\alpha \right\rangle \right|^2 d\mu(\alpha) \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{H}_\tau := \{h \in \mathcal{H} : \langle h, \tau_\alpha \rangle \neq 0, \alpha \in \Omega\}$. Following is the first fundamental result of this paper.

Theorem 2.3. (Continuous Deutsch Uncertainty Principle) Let $(\Omega, \mu), (\Delta, \nu)$ be measure spaces and $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\omega_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ be 1-bounded continuous Parseval frames for a Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Then

$$(3) \quad \log(\mu(\Omega)\nu(\Delta)) \geq S_\tau(h) + S_\omega(h) \geq -2 \log \left(\frac{1 + \sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle \tau_\alpha, \omega_\beta \rangle|}{2} \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_\tau \cap \mathcal{H}_\omega.$$

Proof. Since $1 = \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 d\mu(\alpha)$ for all $h \in \mathcal{H} \setminus \{0\}$, $1 = \int_{\Delta} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 d\nu(\beta)$ for all $h \in \mathcal{H} \setminus \{0\}$ and log is concave, using Jensen's inequality (cf. [6]) we get

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\tau}(h) + S_{\omega}(h) &= \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left(\frac{1}{\left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2} \right) d\mu(\alpha) + \int_{\Delta} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left(\frac{1}{\left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2} \right) d\nu(\beta) \\ &\leq \log \left(\int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 \frac{1}{\left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2} d\mu(\alpha) \right) + \log \left(\int_{\Delta} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 \frac{1}{\left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2} d\nu(\beta) \right) \\ &= \log(\mu(\Omega)) + \log \nu(\Delta) = \log(\mu(\Omega)\nu(\Delta)), \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau} \cap \mathcal{H}_{\omega}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $h \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau} \cap \mathcal{H}_{\omega}$. Then using Buzano inequality [2, 5] we get

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\tau}(h) + S_{\omega}(h) &= - \int_{\Delta} \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 \left[\log \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 + \log \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 \right] d\mu(\alpha) d\nu(\beta) \\ &= - \int_{\Delta} \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 d\mu(\alpha) d\nu(\beta) \\ &= -2 \int_{\Delta} \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right| d\mu(\alpha) d\nu(\beta) \\ &\geq -2 \int_{\Delta} \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left(\left\| \frac{h}{\|h\|} \right\|^2 \frac{\|\tau_{\alpha}\| \|\omega_{\beta}\| + |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \omega_{\beta} \rangle|}{2} \right) d\mu(\alpha) d\nu(\beta) \\ &= -2 \int_{\Delta} \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left(\frac{1 + |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \omega_{\beta} \rangle|}{2} \right) d\mu(\alpha) d\nu(\beta) \\ &\geq -2 \int_{\Delta} \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 \log \left(\frac{1 + \sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \omega_{\beta} \rangle|}{2} \right) d\mu(\alpha) d\nu(\beta) \\ &= -2 \log \left(\frac{1 + \sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \omega_{\beta} \rangle|}{2} \right) \int_{\Delta} \int_{\Omega} \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \tau_{\alpha} \right\rangle \right|^2 \left| \left\langle \frac{h}{\|h\|}, \omega_{\beta} \right\rangle \right|^2 d\mu(\alpha) d\nu(\beta) \\ &\geq -2 \log \left(\frac{1 + \sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \omega_{\beta} \rangle|}{2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 2.3 promotes following question.

Question 2.4. *Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces, $\mathcal{H}$ be a Hilbert space. For which pairs of 1-bounded continuous Parseval frames $\{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ and $\{\omega_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ for $\mathcal{H}$, we have equality in Inequality (3)?*

Based on Theorems 1.3 and Theorem 2.3 we formulate following conjecture.

Conjecture 2.5. (Continuous Kraus Conjecture) *Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces and $\{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$, $\{\omega_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ be 1-bounded continuous Parseval frames for a Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Then*

$$S_{\tau}(h) + S_{\omega}(h) \geq -2 \log \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \omega_{\beta} \rangle| \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H}_{\tau} \cap \mathcal{H}_{\omega}.$$

Next we derive continuous Deutsch uncertainty for Banach spaces. We need a definition.

Definition 2.6. [4] Let (Ω, μ) be a measure space and $\mathcal{X}$ be a Banach space over $\mathbb{K}$. A collection $\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ in $\mathcal{X}^*$ is said to be a **continuous Parseval p-frame** ($1 \leq p < \infty$) for $\mathcal{X}$ if the following conditions hold.

- (i) For each $x \in \mathcal{X}$, the map $\Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto f_\alpha(x) \in \mathbb{K}$ is measurable.
- (ii)

$$\|x\|^p = \int_{\Omega} |f_\alpha(x)|^p d\mu(\alpha), \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}.$$

If $\|\tau_\alpha\| \leq 1, \forall \alpha \in \Omega$, then we say that the frame $\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ is 1-bounded.

Similar to Definition 2.2, we set the following.

Definition 2.7. A continuous Parseval p-frame $\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ for $\mathcal{X}$ is said to be **1-bounded** if

$$\|f_\alpha\| \leq 1, \quad \forall \alpha \in \Omega.$$

Given a 1-bounded continuous Parseval p-frame $\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ for $\mathcal{X}$, we define the **continuous p-Shannon entropy** at a point $x \in \mathcal{X}_f$ as

$$S_f(x) := - \int_{\Omega} \left| f_\alpha \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left| f_\alpha \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p d\mu(\alpha) \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{X}_f := \{x \in \mathcal{X} : f_\alpha(x) \neq 0, \alpha \in \Omega\}$.

Theorem 2.8. (Functional Continuous Deutsch Uncertainty Principle) Let $(\Omega, \mu), (\Delta, \nu)$ be measure spaces and $\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{g_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ be 1-bounded continuous Parseval p-frames for a Banach space $\mathcal{X}$. Then

$$\frac{1}{(\mu(\Omega)\nu(\Delta))^{\frac{1}{p}}} \leq \sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_\alpha(y)g_\beta(y)| \right)$$

and

$$(4) \quad S_f(x) + S_g(x) \geq -p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_\alpha(y)g_\beta(y)| \right) \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g.$$

Proof. Let $z \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $\|z\| = 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= \left(\int_{\Omega} |f_\alpha(z)|^p d\mu(\alpha) \right) \left(\int_{\Delta} |g_\beta(z)|^p d\nu(\beta) \right) = \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} |f_\alpha(z)g_\beta(z)|^p d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_\alpha(y)g_\beta(y)| \right) \right)^p d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\ &= \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_\alpha(y)g_\beta(y)| \right) \right)^p \mu(\Omega)\nu(\Delta) \end{aligned}$$

which gives

$$\frac{1}{\mu(\Omega)\nu(\Delta)} \leq \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_\alpha(y)g_\beta(y)| \right) \right)^p.$$

Let $x \in \mathcal{X}_f \cap \mathcal{X}_g$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
S_f(x) + S_g(x) &= - \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left[\log \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p + \log \left| g_{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \right] d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= - \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) g_{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= -p \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) g_{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right| d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&\geq -p \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(y)g_{\beta}(y)| \right) \right) d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= -p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(y)g_{\beta}(y)| \right) \right) \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p \left| g_{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\|x\|} \right) \right|^p d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= -p \log \left(\sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(y)g_{\beta}(y)| \right) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 2.9. *Theorem 1.1 follows from Theorem 2.8.*

Proof. Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces and $\{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$, $\{\omega_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ be 1-bounded continuous Parseval frames for a Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}$. Define

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{\alpha} : \mathcal{H} \ni h &\mapsto \langle h, \tau_{\alpha} \rangle \in \mathbb{K}; \quad \forall \alpha \in \Omega, \\
g_{\beta} : \mathcal{H} \ni h &\mapsto \langle h, \omega_{\beta} \rangle \in \mathbb{K}, \quad \forall \beta \in \Delta.
\end{aligned}$$

Now by using Buzano inequality [2, 5] we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\sup_{h \in \mathcal{H}, \|h\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(h)g_{\beta}(h)| \right) &= \sup_{h \in \mathcal{H}, \|h\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle h, \tau_{\alpha} \rangle| |\langle h, \omega_{\beta} \rangle| \right) \\
&\leq \sup_{h \in \mathcal{H}, \|h\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} \left(\|h\|^2 \frac{\|\tau_{\alpha}\| \|\omega_{\beta}\| + |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \omega_{\beta} \rangle|}{2} \right) \right) \\
&= \frac{1 + \sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \omega_{\beta} \rangle|}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 2.8 brings the following question.

Question 2.10. *Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces, $\mathcal{X}$ be a Banach space and $p > 1$. For which pairs of continuous Parseval p -frames $\{f_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$, and $\{g_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ for $\mathcal{X}$, we have equality in Inequality (4)?*

Next we derive a dual inequality of (4). For this we need dual of Definition 2.6.

Definition 2.11. *Let (Ω, μ) be a measure space and $\mathcal{X}$ be a Banach space over $\mathbb{K}$. A collection $\{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ in $\mathcal{X}$ is said to be a **continuous Parseval p -frame** ($1 \leq p < \infty$) for $\mathcal{X}^*$ if the following conditions hold.*

- (i) *For each $\phi \in \mathcal{X}^*$, the map $\Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto \phi(\tau_{\alpha}) \in \mathbb{K}$ is measurable.*

(ii)

$$\|f\|^p = \int_{\Omega} |f(\tau_{\alpha})|^p d\mu(\alpha), \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{X}^*.$$

$f \|\tau_{\alpha}\| \leq 1, \forall \alpha \in \Omega$, then we say that the frame $\{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ is 1-bounded.

Given a 1-bounded continuous Parseval p-frame $\{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ for $\mathcal{X}^*$, we define the **continuous p-Shannon entropy** at a point $f \in \mathcal{X}_{\tau}^*$ as

$$S_f(x) := - \int_{\Omega} \left| \frac{f(\tau_{\alpha})}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left| \frac{f(\tau_{\alpha})}{\|f\|} \right|^p d\mu(\alpha) \geq 0,$$

where $\mathcal{X}_{\tau}^* := \{f \in \mathcal{X} : f(\tau_{\alpha}) \neq 0, \alpha \in \Omega\}$. We now have the following dual to Theorem 2.8.

Theorem 2.12. (*Continuous Deutsch Uncertainty Principle for Banach spaces*) Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces and $\{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$, $\{\omega_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ be 1-bounded continuous Parseval p-frames for the dual $\mathcal{X}^*$ of a Banach space $\mathcal{X}$. Then

$$\frac{1}{(\mu(\Omega)\nu(\Delta))^{\frac{1}{p}}} \leq \sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g(\tau_{\alpha})g(\omega_{\beta})| \right)$$

and

$$(5) \quad S_{\tau}(f) + S_{\omega}(f) \geq -p \log \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g(\tau_{\alpha})g(\omega_{\beta})| \right) \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{X}_{\tau}^* \cap \mathcal{X}_{\omega}^*.$$

Proof. Let $h \in \mathcal{X}^*$ be such that $\|h\| = 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= \left(\int_{\Omega} |h(\tau_{\alpha})|^p d\mu(\alpha) \right) \left(\int_{\Delta} |h(\omega_{\beta})|^p d\nu(\beta) \right) = \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} |h(\tau_{\alpha})h(\omega_{\beta})|^p d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g(\tau_{\alpha})g(\omega_{\beta})| \right) \right)^p d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\ &= \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g(\tau_{\alpha})g(\omega_{\beta})| \right) \right)^p \mu(\Omega)\nu(\Delta) \end{aligned}$$

which gives

$$\frac{1}{\mu(\Omega)\nu(\Delta)} \leq \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g(\tau_{\alpha})g(\omega_{\beta})| \right) \right)^p.$$

Let $f \in \mathcal{X}_\tau^* \cap \mathcal{X}_\omega^*$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
S_\tau(f) + S_\omega(f) &= - \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| \frac{f(\tau_\alpha)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_\beta)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left[\log \left| \frac{f(\tau_\alpha)}{\|f\|} \right|^p + \log \left| \frac{f(\omega_\beta)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \right] d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= - \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| \frac{f(\tau_\alpha)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_\beta)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left| \frac{f(\tau_\alpha)}{\|f\|} \frac{f(\omega_\beta)}{\|f\|} \right|^p d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= -p \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| \frac{f(\tau_\alpha)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_\beta)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left| \frac{f(\tau_\alpha)}{\|f\|} \frac{f(\omega_\beta)}{\|f\|} \right| d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&\geq -p \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| \frac{f(\tau_\alpha)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_\beta)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \log \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g(\tau_\alpha)g(\omega_\beta)| \right) \right) d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= -p \log \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g(\tau_\alpha)g(\omega_\beta)| \right) \right) \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Delta} \left| \frac{f(\tau_\alpha)}{\|f\|} \right|^p \left| \frac{f(\omega_\beta)}{\|f\|} \right|^p d\nu(\beta) d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= -p \log \left(\sup_{g \in \mathcal{X}^*, \|g\|=1} \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g(\tau_\alpha)g(\omega_\beta)| \right) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 2.12 again gives the following question.

Question 2.13. *Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces, $\mathcal{X}$ be a Banach space and $p > 1$. For which pairs of continuous Parseval p -frames $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$, and $\{\omega_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ for $\mathcal{X}^*$, we have equality in Inequality (5)*

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